

ENHANCING COGNITIVE BEHAVIOR OF STUDENTS THROUGH KITCHEN GARDEN MODEL - BASED CROP PRODUCTION EDUCATION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 6

Pages: 522-528

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2483

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13928789

Manuscript Accepted: 09-14-2024

Enhancing Cognitive Behavior of Students through Kitchen Garden Model - Based Crop Production Education

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Abstract

This study investigates the integration of the Kitchen Garden Model and its impact on the cognitive behavior of students in crops production. The researcher analyzed respondents' demographic profiles, including sex, age, parents' educational background, and parents' occupation. Additionally, it explored students' perceptions of the Kitchen Garden Model's integration and their cognitive behavior in crop production. Findings revealed a balanced distribution of respondents by sex and age, with many being 16 and 17 years old. Most parents had tertiary education and stable employment, indicating a relatively stable socioeconomic background. Students generally perceived the integration of the Kitchen Garden Model positively, noting high levels of availability, flexibility, engagement, and stability. Their involvement in planting activities, such as nursery operations, planting crops, and crop maintenance, received positive feedback. The study found significant correlations between the Kitchen Garden Model and cognitive behaviors, including environmental consciousness, sustainable agriculture practices, nutrient-dense food utilization, and ecoliteracy. Overall, the integration of the Kitchen Garden Model positively influences students' cognitive behavior in crop production, enhancing their understanding of sustainable practices and promoting environmental consciousness.

Keywords: *kitchen garden model, cognitive behavior, crops production, nutrient dense food, ecoliteracy*

Introduction

The agricultural sector is crucial for the economy, especially in rural areas where most Filipinos live. According to the World Bank (2020), Philippine agriculture can accelerate recovery, reduce poverty, and promote inclusive growth. The Integrated Natural Resources and Environmental Management Project (2016) supports this, noting that agriculture employs about 36% of the workforce. However, the number of farmers is declining.

Literature Review

Challenges

Many Filipino farmers wish their children would pursue other professions (Scientia, 2020). In urban areas, interest in farming is low. Even in rural areas, fewer people want to work on farms. Globally, the percentage of people working in agriculture dropped from 44% in 1991 to 26% in 2020 (International Labor Organization).

Agriculture is the source of the world's food supply, yet we are losing our ability to contribute effectively. Despite rich natural resources, 64% of the Philippine population is chronically food insecure, the highest in Southeast Asia (Integrated Food Security Situation, 2020). Over 54.9 million Filipinos suffer from poor food consumption quality, quantity, and high undernutrition levels.

Many city residents lacked access to fresh vegetables. A survey by the Food and Nutrition Research Institute (2020) found that 62.1% of Filipino households experienced moderate to severe food insecurity in 2020. In 2019, the Philippines imported 3 million tons of food during the pandemic (United States Department of Agriculture Foreign Service). Everyone must learn crop production skills, whether in rural or urban areas. Teachers should cultivate these skills to help students connect with nature when needed.

Educational Interventions

The Philippines has introduced several educational initiatives to strengthen agricultural education and encourage youth involvement in farming. Programs like the "Young Farmers Challenge Fund" support young entrepreneurs in agriculture. Schools are integrating agricultural education into their curricula, emphasizing hands-on learning and the use of technology in farming. Partnerships with agricultural research institutions provide students with access to the latest innovations.

Benefits of Kitchen Garden Model

Kitchen garden can address food insecurity and promote sustainable living. Alexander (2004) proposed it to combat obesity in Australia. This model involves growing vegetables at home using available space and containers. Steps include identifying space, choosing containers, selecting crops, getting the right soil, and planting. The hands-on nature of kitchen gardening can develop learners' interest in crop production.

Implementing a kitchen garden model in education can have significant cognitive and behavioral benefits. Hands-on gardening activities enhance memory retention and understanding of biological processes. They also encourage problem-solving skills and

promote healthier eating habits by increasing awareness of food sources. This can lead to increased consumption of fruits and vegetables, improving overall nutrition. According to Rana (2021), kitchen gardens enhance household nutritional security. They help tackle malnutrition and micronutrient deficiencies. Implementing this model in urban schools can sustain food security and nurture agricultural skills in students.

The integration of the Kitchen Garden Model represents a novel approach to fostering cognitive behavior among students in crops production. This innovative educational strategy seeks to engage students in hands-on learning experiences within the world of agriculture, aiming to deepen their understanding of crop cultivation while simultaneously enhancing their cognitive behavior. In 2019, Wallace's research suggested that gaining a deep understanding of the Kitchen Garden Model resulted in heightened awareness of plant changes, extending beyond the garden setting. This familiarity also cultivated increased empathy towards living organisms and a greater appreciation for the natural environment.

Agricultural Competencies in Education

The Department of Education outlines four key agricultural competencies for students: 1) Perform nursery operations, 2) Plant crops, 3) Care for and maintain crops, 4) Harvest and post-harvest activities.

Role of Teachers

Teachers of Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.) have a duty to cultivate agricultural skills in urban students. This motivated the researcher to conduct this study to address food insecurity, promote sustainable living, enhance health and nutrition, foster entrepreneurship, reconnect with nature, and build community resilience. By cultivating this behavior, students are empowered to lead healthier, more self-sufficient, and sustainable lives.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, a descriptive correlational research design was employed to observe the development of cognitive behavior in Grade 10 students during crop production activities. The study utilized several instruments to gather necessary data, including an evaluation sheet and a learning plan specific to crop production, to ensure the research goals were achieved.

The research integrated the kitchen garden model as a learning prototype to develop cognitive behaviors that enhance students' understanding of ecological sustainability, promote hands-on experiences, and foster critical thinking skills in practical life applications.

Respondents

A purposive sampling technique was applied in this study, including the total population of three Grade 10 sections: 10 Charity, 10 Fidelity, and 10 Peace. These sections, comprising 106 students, were chosen as they were handled by the researcher during the 2023-2024 school year, providing a comprehensive sample for the study.

Instrument

To gather relevant data, the researcher employed various techniques to integrate the kitchen garden model in Grade 10 students' cognitive development in crop production.

The questionnaire, validated by teachers and experts, was presented to a panel for final checking and approval. The questionnaire included:

Part I: Respondent profile (Sex, Age, Parents' Educational Background, Parents' Occupation).

Part II: Perceptions of the Kitchen Garden Model's integration in terms of availability, flexibility, engagement, and stability.

Part III: Perceptions of the integration through actual planting activities (nursery operations, planting, care and maintenance, harvesting, post-harvest).

Part IV: Cognitive behavior in crop production (environmental consciousness, sustainable agriculture mindset, utilization of nutrient-dense foods, ecoliteracy).

Procedure

To achieve the study's objectives, the researcher followed a series of steps. Initially, permission was sought from the Dean's Office of Laguna State Polytechnic University College of Teacher Education to conduct the study. After internal and external validation, the instruments were presented to the Principal of Maryhill College, Lucena City, for approval.

Upon receiving approval, the researcher sought an appropriate area within the campus to establish a school garden. This space was selected to ensure adequate room for containers, sunlight, air circulation, and water access. This systematic approach ensured the study was conducted rigorously, leading to meaningful and reliable results.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Distribution of profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex*

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	52	49.06
Female	54	50.94
Total	106	100.0

The data in Table 1 indicates a fairly balanced distribution of respondents by sex, with 52 male students (49.06%) and 54 female students (50.94%) out of a total of 106 respondents. This slight predominance of female respondents ensures a balanced perspective in the study.

Table 2. *Distribution of profile of the Respondents in terms of Age*

Age	Frequency	Percent
13 and below	-	-
14	-	-
15	6	5.66
16	43	40.57
17	39	36.79
18 and above	18	16.98
Total	106	100.0

The data in Table 2 presents the age profile of the respondents, with the majority being 16 years old (40.57%) and 17 years old (36.79%). There were no respondents aged 13 and below, while 15-year-olds accounted for 5.66%, and those 18 years and above constituted 16.98%. This distribution indicates that most respondents fall within the 16 to 17-year-old age range.

Table 3. *Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Educational Background*

	Frequency		Percent	
	Father	Mother	Father	Mother
Elementary Undergraduate	1	2	0.94	1.89
Elementary Graduate	2	-	1.89	-
Highschool Undergraduate	3	1	2.83	0.94
Highschool Graduate	6	7	5.66	6.60
Tertiary Undergraduate	5	11	4.72	10.38
Tertiary Graduate	89	85	83.96	80.19
Total	106	50	100.0	100.0

Table 3 describes the educational backgrounds of the respondents' parents. The majority of fathers (83.96%) and mothers (80.19%) have completed tertiary education. A smaller percentage have lower educational levels, with 5.66% of fathers and 6.60% of mothers having completed high school. This indicates a high level of parental education among the respondents.

Table 4. *Distribution of the respondents in terms of Parent's Occupation*

	Frequency		Percent	
	Father	Mother	Father	Mother
Unemployed	11	4	10.38	3.77
Self-employed	22	25	20.75	23.58
Employed	73	77	68.87	72.64
Total	106	106	100.00	100.00

Table 4 shows that the majority of respondents' fathers (68.87%) and mothers (72.64%) are employed. A smaller percentage of fathers (20.75%) and mothers (23.58%) are self-employed, while 10.38% of fathers and 3.77% of mothers are unemployed. This suggests that most parents are employed, reflecting an urban environment. Consequently, students tend to gravitate towards professions that are align with the urban context in which they are raised. This preference is shaped by the practical relevance and opportunities available in their environment, influencing their career choices towards fields that are more typical or accessible within such settings.

Table 5. *Summary of the respondents' perception in the integration of Kitchen Garden Model*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
Availability	3.55	0.40	Always observed
Flexibility	3.60	0.33	Always observed
Engagement	3.63	0.27	Always observed
Stability	3.59	0.25	Always observed
Overall	3.59	0.05	Always observed

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Not Observed), 1.76-2.50 (Rarely Observed), 2.51-3.25 (Sometimes Observed), 3.26-4.0- (Always Observed)

Table 5 shows that all indicators of the integration of the Kitchen Garden Model—availability, flexibility, engagement, and stability—are "Always Observed" by the respondents, with overall means ranging from 3.55 to 3.63. Engagement had the highest mean (3.63), indicating strong student involvement. The overall mean score of 3.59 demonstrates a consistent positive perception of the Kitchen Garden Model's integration.

Table 6. Summary of the respondents' perception in the integration of Kitchen Garden Model through the actual planting

Indicator	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
Perform nursery operations	3.57	0.36	Always observed
Plant crops	3.59	0.29	Always observed
Care and maintain crops	3.55	0.21	Always observed
Carry out harvest	3.40	0.20	Always observed
Post-harvest	3.52	0.16	Always observed
Overall	3.53	0.07	Always observed

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Not Observed), 1.76-2.50 (Rarely Observed), 2.51-3.25 (Sometimes Observed), 3.26-4.0- (Always Observed)

Table 6 reveals that all aspects of the Kitchen Garden Model's integration through actual planting are "Always Observed" by the respondents. Planting crops received the highest mean score (3.59), while carrying out harvest had the lowest (3.40). This suggests that while planting is well-received, there is room to enhance the harvesting process. The overall mean score of 3.53 indicates a generally positive perception of the planting activities.

Table 7. Summary of the respondents' cognitive behavior in crops production

Indicator	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
Environmental Consciousness	3.38	0.18	Always
Honing students' mindset in sustainable agriculture practice	3.38	0.23	Always
Utilization of nutrient dense food	3.48	0.28	Always
Ecoliteracy	3.59	0.23	Always
Overall	3.46	0.04	Always

Legend: 1.0-1.75 (Never), 1.76-2.50 (Rarely), 2.51-3.25 (Sometimes), 3.26-4.0- (Always)

Table 7 shows that all indicators of cognitive behavior—environmental consciousness, sustainable agriculture mindset, utilization of nutrient-dense foods, and ecoliteracy—are "Always" observed. Ecoliteracy had the highest mean score (3.59), indicating a strong understanding of ecological principles among respondents. The overall mean score of 3.46 reflects a consistent demonstration of cognitive behaviors in crop production.

Table 8. Significant relationship between the student's perception in the integration of Kitchen Garden Model and cognitive behavior in crops production

Correlations Integration of Kitchen Garden Model	Environmental Consciousness	Honing students' mindset in sustainable agriculture practice	Utilization of nutrient dense food	Ecoliteracy
Availability;	-.084	.094	.540**	.481**
Flexibility;	-.176	.049	.464**	.452**
Engagement;	-.136	.165	.540**	.434**
Stability;	-.122	.151	.649**	.494**
Perform nursery operations;	.110	.348**	.830**	.652**
Plant crops;	.014	.373**	.780**	.530**
Care and maintain crops;	.204	.371**	.623**	.334**
Carry out harvest; and	.078	.265**	.599**	.554**
Post-harvest	.141	.079	.587**	.459**

Table 8 presents the correlations between students' perceptions of the Kitchen Garden Model and various cognitive behaviors. There is a strong positive correlation between the integration of the Kitchen Garden Model and the utilization of nutrient-dense foods (correlation coefficients ranging from 0.464 to 0.830). Moderate positive correlations are observed with environmental consciousness and sustainable agriculture practices. This indicates that practical activities in the Kitchen Garden Model significantly enhance students' cognitive behaviors related to crop production.

The data from the tables provide a comprehensive view of the respondents' demographics, perceptions, and cognitive behaviors related to the Kitchen Garden Model. The balanced sex distribution, predominant age range of 16-17 years, and high parental education levels are notable. Most parents are employed, reflecting an urban setting. The integration of the Kitchen Garden Model is positively perceived across all indicators, with strong engagement and consistent positive cognitive behaviors observed. Significant positive correlations highlight the model's impact on enhancing students' understanding and application of agricultural concepts, particularly in utilizing nutrient-dense foods and developing ecoliteracy. These findings underscore the effectiveness of the Kitchen Garden Model in fostering practical and cognitive skills in crop production among students.

Conclusions

In summary, the integration of the Kitchen Garden Model into educational curricula positively influences students' cognitive behavior in crop production, enhancing their practical skills, environmental consciousness, and understanding of sustainable agriculture practices. These findings support the beneficial impact of such models in educational settings, although the hypothesis that there would be no significant impact is not sustained. Consequently, the study recommends the continued and expanded use of the Kitchen Garden Model to enrich students' educational experiences and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

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